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**Pastoral Pitfalls and Its Implications on
Church Growth in Nigeria**

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Abstract

This work accentuated that the moral and spiritual virtues of many pastors in Nigeria have deteriorated in recent times, and this has dire consequences on the life of the Church. The research is aimed at unravelling the implications of pastoral pitfalls on Church growth and to proffer possible solutions to the menace. Using descriptive phenomenology, the study uncovered that lack of proper theological training and formation, distractions and discouragement, self-control, adherence to biblical virtues, spiritual laziness, and giving in to societal pressure and standard, are some of the reasons why pastors stray from the main calling into the ministry. Consequently, these have negatively affected the general spirituality of the society; stunted church growth, and brought about personal and family reproaches. The work recommended that obedience to the word of God, self-control, discipline, mentoring and openness to the Holy Spirit and personal spiritual development can go a long way in addressing pitfalls among pastors. The pastor should be a man of secret prayer and exacted piety, a man of sound Biblical principles and strong persuasion about his ministry and that the family of the pastor should be contented with the resources available to them. The church, the family of the pastor, as well as the entire society should play a supportive role to pastoral ministry to avoid the temptation of falling away. This way, the life of Church will be restored and growth will be seamless.

Keywords: Pastors, Pitfall, Christianity, Church Growth, Nigeria

Introduction

One of the major news headlines that floods our national dailies and other social media platforms, is the news related to pastoral misdemeanour. While other incidents may attract less attention, that of a pastor may not. It is usually hyped, and sometimes beyond proportion. This is so, because pastors are expected to maintain high moral and spiritual standard and integrity in the society. While not justifying pastors' moral ineptitude, pastoral pitfalls go to affirm that they too are vulnerable to error and temptations. It is out of place (though it ought to be so) to think that pastors are free from sexual temptation, fear of man, envy, greed, pride, anger, bitterness, and idolatry, among others. However, when a pastor is involved in any of the mentioned misconducts, the impact is usually devastating on the congregation, as it retards growth. His family and the entire society, are badly affected. Asserting the above views, Hull (2007) opined that, "in far too many instances, clerics in privileged positions to shepherd the sheep themselves flounder in aimlessness and frustration."

The pastor has as his sole business, the responsibility to expand the Kingdom frontiers. This mandate of the Church, which the pastor is charged to carry out is to, 'make disciples of all nations' (Matthew 28:19). On this, Maxey (1987) postulated that:

The foremost responsibility of a pastor, is to keep clear in his own heart what it takes to produce a spirit-filled Church: a Church devoted to prayer, intercession, thanksgiving, praise, witnessing boldly at home, schools, and shops, devoted to sacrifice of time, money and talents; a membership with missionary vision and burden for the lost, heeding the admonition, 'Go ye into all the world and preach the gospel.'

Unfortunately, there is a total deviation from the main objectives of the ministry mandate by many pastors today. It is this shift from the core mandate that has resulted in the many pitfalls witnessed among pastors in Nigeria. For the pastor to perform the function of producing a spirit-filled congregation, his life and character must conform to his preaching and pastoral activities.

Today, many pastors in Nigeria, are enmeshed with myriads negative trends of immorality, idolatry, financial impropriety, drunkenness, pride,

disobedience and all forms of rivalry and competitions. Thus, many shades of worldly conformity most detrimental to the spiritual influence have infiltrated the ranks and files of the clergy and corrupted the dignity and integrity of ministry and mission work (Bridges, 1980). The result of pastoral pitfalls includes but not limited to, division in the church, dwindling membership, lukewarmness, spiritual lethargy, loss of confidence in the Church, family problems, among others.

The aim of this research is to examine the implications of pastoral pitfalls on Church growth in Nigeria and to proffer possible solution on how this menace can be mitigated. The methodology adopted was that of descriptive phenomenology. Secondary sources of data collection were used in gathering necessary information relevant for this work. The work affirmed that a healthy growing Church is a replica of the life and ministry of her pastor. When the opposite is the case, then, the life of the pastor should be checked. In the next sub-heading, the researcher will consider few salient concepts that formed the nexus of the study.

Delineating the Key Concepts

Under this subheading, the concepts of pastor, pitfall and Church growth, shall be examined. The word 'pastor' from Greek etymology is known as *poimen* (Eph. 4:11). It simply means to care, shepherd or someone who keeps animals. Sometimes, it is used to indicate those chosen by God to feed, lead, and care for the "flock" of Christ (Brand, Draper, and England, 2003). Furthermore, Youngblood (1995), and Still (1996), noted that the pastor is one who feeds, protects, and guides or shepherds the flock of God's people. Thus, going by this positions, one can conveniently say that pastors are shepherds, ministers of the Word, feeders, guides, protectors, leaders, and caretakers of the flock of Christ (Abafi, 20020).

On the other hand, pitfall by definition, means a hidden danger or trap. It is often used to denote situations or temptations that could mislead one if care is not taken. When applied to pastors, it relates to the idea of one not comprehending the context or meaning of Scriptures, which can lead to misinterpretations and wrong application (Bible.org, 2010). To Adoyi (2022), pitfall means, a danger or difficulty, especially one that is not obvious at first and can cause havoc. It is an invisible pit figuratively dug spiritually or emotionally, targeting the down fall of its victims, in this context, the pastor.

Church growth, according to Igboin and Adedibu, (2020), “is that science which investigates the nature, function and health of the Christian church in terms of expansion.” Nmah and Otubah (2024) citing Hunter (1983), maintained that the church is a living organism. It is a community of saints, a “communion sanctorum.” Not just a building or resting place but a people and as a living organism, it is expected to grow, all things being equal (Uka, 1995, Nmah and Otubah, 2024). Thus, church growth is a historical process examining how the church has fared in terms of growth and in its attempt to spread the gospel, since the early times till today. Christianity has grown so widely that it has reached every continent of the world (Falk, 1997).

An Overview of Pitfalls among Pastors Today

There is plethora of pastoral pitfalls in the contemporary society, but a few of them shall be suffice in what follows:

1. ***Sexual Immorality:*** Sexual immorality is one of the key dangers that pastors fall into. This pitfall, has done a lot of damage to pastoral ministry today. Sexual misconduct includes both sexual abuse and sexual harassment. Akerele (2022), observed that a lot of pastors are using sex as a church growth ritual. Some are trapped in it as a work of the flesh because of the distorted doctrine they have been fed with. Adedoyin (2015), noted that pastors involved in sexual misdemeanour take advantage of their position to indulge in sexual misconduct with their female congregations or even with a minor. Kane (2013), said that, it includes sexual malfeasance, which means any voluntary sexual activity in which there is a breach of trust between clergy and member within a professional relationship. The consequences of sex scandals involving the pastors in the church have been lethal and fatal, cutting across all segments of the society (Akerele, 2022).
2. ***Pride:*** Pride, according to Jamieso (2022), is one common pitfall for pastors today. Pride simply means one thinking too highly of oneself. Lewis (2001) argues that pride is the “essential vice,” leading to enmity with God, whether pastors or anyone. Mathis (2019) affirmed that one of the few things that poison the church, and sully her reputation in the world, is arrogance of pastors. It is a great blight on the church and in the community where the church is to shine as the light of the world. *Swelling pride in a leader endangers the whole church.* Crouse (2020) described some enabling factors that can subtly lead to this kind of

pastoral pitfall. Pastors' gifts, eloquence, and position are perfect subtle factors that can lead to pride.

3. ***Professionalism:*** Battzig (2017) noted that the mentality of professionalism, is one of the problems pastors face today. This should not be associated with the pastor, as they are servants of God. Professionalism has nothing to do with the essence and heart of the Christian ministry. The more professional pastors long to be, the more spiritual death they will experience. Thus, thinking professionalism by pastors is a pitfall. (Ministry Magazine, 1961). When pastoral ministry is compared to business outfit, the problem associated with it is endemic. The church is not a business like any other, despite its organizational and financial aspects. The church does not sell products. The minister is not a business man. He is a servant of God with the mandate to represent God on earth. The professionalizing of pastoral work in any form or shape the bane of the church's existence (Batzig, 2017).
4. ***Impatience and Desire to Make Change:*** Segal (2021) said that, impatience is a dark and prevalent sin among pastors that is usually explained away. It is a product of human pride and unbelief, seen in most pastors, as a result of frustration that one does not control what happens in one's life. In the same vein, Jamieso (2022), noted that, plenty of God's work often carried out in human lives takes time. Sometimes God uses setbacks, detours and sufferings to achieve His aims in human lives and pastors should not think that God is delaying their process. So, waiting on the Lord is part God's plan and programmes for pastors. Moses spent forty years in the wilderness twice, to have God's commandment delivered to the Israelites.
5. ***Lack of Accountability and Self-control:*** Another pastoral pitfall witnessed today is that of lack of accountability and self-control. This menace has really pervaded the church ministry. French (2014), lamented in expectation that, there should always be pastors and leaders who can tell the truth. Running from accountability is a sure sign of spiritual turmoil on the part of a pastor. Self-control is a vital ability the ministry should exhibit even in areas that may or may not be classified as sinful. Impulsiveness may be charming, but it is also dangerous, especially when pastors are tasked with caring for the well-being of others. Finance and temper are two areas that are often

troublesome for ministers who struggle with self-control. Furthermore, self-control is a fruit of the Spirit (Galatians 5:22-23). If self-control is not evident in the pastor's life, it is symptomatic of deeper problems lurking under the surface.

Factors Responsible for Pastoral Pitfalls

Some factors can be adduced as reasons why pastors derail from their calling in ministry. Few of such reasons include: lack of proper training for the ministry, abuse of authority, corruption, financial issues, distraction and discouragement and neglecting personal spiritual development.

1. ***Lack of Proper Training:*** Tribune (2017), asserts that lack of proper ministerial training has the tendency of affecting the effectiveness of pastoral agents in serving their congregations and navigating complex situations within the church community. Those seeking to occupy the pastoral roles, are expected to receive basic training and skills development necessary for effective functioning. Lack of it could lead to pitfalls. Akin-John (2017), emphasized that pastors who desire to eschew pitfalls in ministry should be trained on biblical interpretations, pulpit mannerism and pulpit delivery and communication. Pastors should have insight on social media and internet usage, church planting, leadership, relationship, dispute resolution and crises management among others. Pastors aspiring healthy output, should undergo training that develops character, knowledge, personality, communication, relationship and congregation. Lack of these will land such pastors into avoidable challenges and pitfalls (Akin-John, 2017).
2. ***Abuse of Pastoral Authority and Influence:*** Many pastors today are culpable of this pitfall. Abuse of pastoral authority occurs when pastors use their influence to inflict pains on their members. This is in form of psychological, spiritual and emotional damage suffered by members of authoritarian communities of faith, using unethical, cruel and damaging means (Essien, 2010). Sometimes these may be physical or sexual in nature, but much more often, it is seen in the many various forms of mental and spiritual trauma that are inflicted upon church members. The truth remains that pastors who act as dictators are not fulfilling a calling of God but are instead elevating themselves into a position to serve their own self-interests and

ambitions. They go outside of the biblical teachings for the purpose of fulfilling their desires to control the lives of others (Essien, 2010).

3. **Corruption:** Another important factor responsible for pastoral pitfalls is the prevalence of corruption in the land. Familusi (2010), asserted that corruption in Nigeria, has pervaded the religious environment tremendously. He went on to affirm that people even worship in a corrupt Church, and to an extent, by corrupt pastors. Consequently, the socio-religious implications of corruption in Nigeria becomes innumerable. This has cast some doubts about the future of the Church in Nigeria today and beyond (Oluwatusin, 2020). It is pathetic to remark that a major contemporary manifestation of corruption is schism, which has been taken to a ridiculous extent. Members of the church are usually exploited, impoverished, by the commercialization of spiritual items like anointing oil and others. It has become a scenario where ministries are registered in family names, with the family members overseeing the entire successive leadership of the church. This has become a soft point for pastoral pitfalls in Nigeria (Familusi 2010).
4. **Materialism and Money Matters:** The love of money has unduly swayed the messages of many pastors, damaged their credibility, or even sunk their ministry entirely, because they failed to pay close attention to money matters in ministry. Pastors should not be focused on financially profiting from ministry. This is a trap that has caught many unaware and ruined their pastoral vocation (Bredenhof, 2021). Paul was mindful of how the love of money can have a corrupting influence on a pastor's ministry. He warned the Church and her pastors to be mindful of it. He went ahead to denounce those who peddle the Word of God for personal profit (2 Cor. 2:17). It is still incumbent on churches today to faithfully support the gospel ministry being done in their midst. Such assistance allows pastors to devote much of their time to the task of serving the church. They can do so without being distracted by material cares or occupied with labours that are unrelated to ministry. While the Church is encouraged to support her pastors financially, pastors should avoid the temptation of embezzling or siphoning church fund for personal aggrandizement.
5. **Distractions & Discouragement:** Discussing the error of distraction and discouragement, Harvey (2024), said that pastors have more tasks, communication, and job expectations to carry out today, than

ever before. This makes distractions and discouragement two of the most significant mental challenges and pitfalls in ministry. *Postell (2022)*, noted that pastors often face myriads of challenges related to distraction and discouragement, coming from the demanding nature of their job, this includes constant pressure to perform, deal with complex interpersonal issues, and navigate the expectations of a diverse congregation, often leading to feelings of overwhelm and a lack of focus on their core ministry work. All these can weigh the pastor down and lead him to committing error while discharging his duties. To avoid this, churches should encourage and support their pastors. Pastors as well should be intentional with their schedules, willing to delegate auxiliary tasks, and creating a working environment that promotes encouragement (Harvey, 2024).

6. ***Neglecting Personal Spiritual Development:*** One significant danger in ministry is that some pastors channel their energy on studying and building others up spiritually; thus, neglecting to work on their personal spirituality. This naturally creates a weak spiritual framework for pastor's lives, where others are fed spiritually, while they remain hungry. To avoid this weakness, pastors must maintain personal Bible study directed towards their needs. They are to do away with the chasm of prayerlessness (French, 2014). DeYoung (2013), noted that when pastors neglect their personal devotion, it means they are failing to prioritize regular, dedicated time alone with God through prayer and Bible study. This can lead to a decline in their own spiritual health and ability to effectively minister to others in their congregation. In order to fight this particular temptation, pastors should devote time to study and pray regularly.

Pastoral Pitfalls Impinging Church Growth

Churches rise and fall on her pastors. The lifestyle of pastors plays a crucial role in shaping the dynamics of church communities and influencing congregational growth. Various studies have highlighted that the personal conduct, spiritual integrity, and overall lifestyle of pastors significantly affect the faith and commitment of church members, leading to overall growth.

One of the major indices of Church growth is evangelism. When this is affected by pastor's lifestyle, it brings stunted growth for the church. Adedoyin (2015), noted that pastoral pitfall makes the evangelistic effort of

the church unfruitful. When a pastor commits adultery or fornication, it will be difficult for such a church to evangelize. People always find it difficult to attend or listen to churches whose pastors are enmeshed in any form of scandal and this is not healthy for church growth (Job Adeyemo, oral communication, 15th September, 2014).

HI Writers (n.d), observed that the prevalence of immorality among pastors in Nigeria has become alarming. It has grown to a level that creates fear and tension in the heart of anyone who has concern for the future church growth in Nigeria. According to New Testament of the Holy Bible, jealousy, killing, lies, adultery, fornication, theft, heresies, pride and several immoral acts are against the will of God and hinder the progress of church mission. The bastardisation, abuse and mismanagement of wealth among ministers through ostentatious lifestyle, has given reasons for concern in Nigerian churches today. This act has created unhealthy competitions among several ministers that the gospel being preached in most churches today are one sided (anchoring more on prosperity) and no longer balanced with godly and righteous living with self-discipline, which is the hallmark of Christian faith (Omenazu, 2022).

Another critical ethical issue of church growth in Nigeria borders on the fact that church leadership and membership do hardly bother about public perception of the church, and their relationship with outsiders. This is critical because one of the criteria used by the early church to appoint leaders is that they must have honest report among the people (Acts 6:3). Paul also elaborates the criteria and expectations (Tit. 1:5-9; 1 Tim. 3:1-13), emphasizing good report even from people outside the church. Little attention has actually been given to this very important criterion in church growth discourse. The consequence of this has been well articulated by Kinnaman (2012), who concludes that it is unchristian. Studies show that many people outside of Christianity, especially younger adults, have little trust in the Christian faith, and esteem for the lifestyle of Christ's followers is quickly fading in the society. The fact is that the lifestyle of pastors in churches has become a barrier for many people who would have loved to be converted, thereby disrupting church growth (Igboin and Adedibu, 2020).

Mitigating Pastoral Pitfalls

The need to mitigating pastoral pitfalls has become very essential for Church growth. Steps towards ameliorating this hinge on a lot factors,

ranging from the formative stage in ministry to daily personal spiritual development of pastoral agents.

Abafi (2020), emphasized the importance of proper pastoral training, as this will help pastors avoid error capable of destroying their ministry. Pastors are expected to be trained to ensure that the right message is passed on to their congregations in order to build them up and help them stand against pitfalls that are virtually bedeviling the church today. To be a good pastor, one's life must be spent in knowing the truth of God's word, not only verbally, propositionally, and theologically, religiously, devotionally, morally, and otherwise (Abafi, 2020). Prime (1995), suggests that formal training is part of the preparation for the ministry and must be put to the test by those responsible for the training.

Another area of great importance is the worship life of a pastor. The ministers themselves must make sure that they cast their trust in God and live by example. Pastors who are involved in sin cannot give God true worship; neither can they promote it, because no one can give what he or she does not have (Abafi, 2020).

To mitigate pastoral pitfalls, prayer and fasting are key. Aransiola (1999), noted that the major reason why a lot of pastors, including other believers today are unsuccessful, stagnant and amount to nothing in life, is because they do not have altar of prayer. A pastor is not greater than his altar. The success, advancement, increase and consequent breakthrough in every area of life of a pastor is dependent upon his altar of prayer.

Thompson (1995), noted that fasting is cleansing. It cleans out the bodies. It lays bare the souls. It leads the pastors into the arms of God and draws them nearer to Him. When this happens, there is hunger and thirst for justice, for goodness and holiness, for Church growth. Through fasting, pastors put to death earthly desires and long only for the heavenly.

Constant engagement in evangelism can help pastors avoid pitfalls in many respects. In Matthew 5:16, Jesus told His disciples to allow their light shine before men so that they can see their good deeds and praise God, their Father in heaven. Pastors must show the light of God for others to see. The lives of pastors must be a natural overflow of the Christian life. Whitney (1991), noted that evangelism is a discipline and that pastors must discipline themselves to get into the context of evangelism, as this will go a long way in assisting them overcome temptations to sin.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The fact of pastoral pitfall is really evident among members of the clergy in Nigeria. When pastors fall or indulge in any form of crime and immoral behaviour, the attention it draws sometimes outweighs the crime itself. This is because of the high moral, ethical and spiritual integrity expected of pastors in the society. Lack of proper training and formation, misuse of power and authority, distraction and discouragement, not paying attention to spiritual development among others, can lead pastors to various degrees of misconduct.

The impact of pastoral pitfalls is usually germane. It is very endemic and negatively affects the entire society, not excluding the family of the pastor, but more regrettably, retards Church growth. To mitigate this menace, the pastors have to be focused on the essence of their calling, develop a level of spiritual exercise capable of helping them avoid hidden error in their pastoral carrier.

The work further recommends that: Pastors should consciously place self under solemn obligation to live exacted life of piety. By this he should be a man of transparent honesty and purity. Pastors should be men of sound Biblical principles, studious and prayerful. Contentment on the part of the family of the pastor will encourage calmness. Pastors should have a strong persuasion and should receive a strong backing from the family. The church and the society should play a supportive role to pastoral ministry. This way, the pastor will be on his way to fulfilling his calling into the ministry; and the church of God will grow naturally.

References

- Abafi, A.M.G. (2020). Effects of pastors' lifestyle on church members: case study of GYEL local church council of evangelical church winning all. D.Min Thesis Submitted To Asbury Theological Seminary
- Adedoyin, A.D. (2015). Sexual immorality among pastors and its implications to the local church: A case study of Ogbomosho Baptist conference. https://www.Academia.Edu/113399088/Sexual_Immorality_Among_Pastors_And_Its_Implications_To_The_Local_Church_A_Case_Study_Of_Ogbomosho_Baptist_Conference?AutoDownload
- Adoyi, G.O. (2022). Examination of the causes and effects of pastoral pitfalls in Methodist church Nigeria, Zonkwa circuit, Kaduna state. DMin Thesis submitted to Wesley University Ondo

- Akerele, A. (2022). Sexual immorality and the church.
<https://www.Premiumtimesng.Com/Opinion/508738-Sexual-Immorality-And-The-Church-By-Ayo-Akerele.Html?Tztc=1>
- Akin-John, F.B. (2017). Why we need to train, retrain pastors.
<https://Tribuneonlineg.Com/Need-Train-Retrain-Pastors/>
- Aransiola, M. O. (1999). *The secrets of breakthrough prayers*. Ibadan: Gethsemane Publication. Ibadan.
- Batzig, N.T (2017). Being professional in ministry? <https://Feedingonchrist.Org/A-Professional-Ministry/>
- Brand, C.; Draper, C. & England, A. (2003). General Editors. Holman Illustrated Bible Dictionary. Nashville, Tennessee: Holman Bible Publisher.
- Bredenhof, B. (2021). Churches, pastors, and money.
<https://Www.Modernreformation.Org/Resources/Articles/Churches-Pastors-And-Money>
- Bridges, C. (1980). *The Christian ministry*. Pennsylvania: The Banner of Truth Trust.
- Crouse, P. (2020). Pastors, beware of pride https://Ftc.Co/Resource-Library/BlogEntries/Pastors-Beware-Of-Pride/#_Ftn1
- Deyoung, K. (2013). The Danger Of Neglecting Word And Prayer In Gospel Ministry <https://Guardthedeposit.Com/2013/01/Danger-Neglecting-Word-Prayer-Gospel-Ministry/>
- Essen, A.M. (2010). Proliferation of Churches: A leeway to commercialization of religion. *European Journal of Scientific Research* 4(4).
- Familusi. O.O (2010). Corruption and pastoral ministry in the 21st century.
- Falk, P. (1997). *The growth of the church*. Bukuru: Acts
- French, R.A. (2014). 5 ministry pitfalls. <https://Ryana french.Com/Ministry-Pitfalls/>
- Harvey, J (2024). Top 10 challenges facing pastors.
<https://www.Subsplash.Com/Blog/Pastor-Problems>
- HI writers (n.d) Immorality in the church and its effects on church growth.
<https://Hiwriters.Com.Ng/Product/Immorality-In-The-Church-And-Its-Effects-On-Church-Growth/>
- Hull, B. (2007). *The disciple-making pastor*. Michigan: Grand Rapids.
- Hunter, K.R. (1983). *Foundations for church growth*. New Haven: Leader Publishing Company.
- Igboin, B. and Adedibu, B.A. (2020). Christian ethics and sustainable church growth in Nigeria. *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies (Jais)*: Issn 2523-6725 (Online) May 2020 Vol. 4, No. 5
- Jamieson, B. (2022). Common pitfalls on the path to becoming a pastor.
<https://www.Crossway.Org/Articles/Common-Pitfalls-On-The-Path-To-Becoming-A-Pastor/>
- Kane, M. (2013). Catholic priests' knowledge of pastoral codes of conduct in the United States. *Ethics & Behaviour* Volume 23, Issue 3.

- Mathis, D. (2019). Pride disqualifies a pastor.
<https://www.Desiringgod.Org/Articles/Pride-Disqualifies-A-Pastor>
- Maxey, I. P. (1987). *Ministerial ethics and etiquette*. Ohio: Schmul Publishing Co. Inc.
- Ministry Magazine, (1961) Pitfalls of the ministry.
<https://www.Ministrymagazine.Org/Archive/1961/09/Pitfalls-Of-The-Ministry>
- Nmah, P.E. and Otubah, G. I. (2024). The pathology of church growth in Igbo land, Nigeria: an antidote to the symptoms. *Acjol.Org*
- Omenazu, E. (2022). Impact of gospel ministers' lifestyles on church growth in Nigeria. <https://Independent.Ng/Impact-Of-Gospel-Ministers-Lifestyles-On-Church-Growth-In-Nigeria/>
- Oluwatusin, C.O. (2020). An examination of corruption in Nigeria and the prospect of pastoral ministry. *Light in a once-dark world* Volume 3, November.
<https://www.Biblicaltheology.Com/Light/An%20examination%20of%20corruption%20in%20nigeria%20and%20the%20prospect%20of%20pastoral%20ministry.Pdf>
- Oyetade, M. (2013). The abuse of pastoral authority in some churches in Nigeria today. In *Uma Journal of Philosophy & Religious Studies*.
<https://www.Academia.Edu/103265169/The-Abuse-Of-Pastoral-Authority-In-Some-Churches-In-Nigeria-Today?Auto=Download>
- Postell, M. (2022). Stress tops mental challenges pastors face.
<https://Research.Lifeway.Com/2022/04/26/Stress-Tops-Mental-Challenges-Pastors-Face/>
- Prabhudas, K., (2014). Church leaders' pitfall –part 1.
<https://Gethsemaneipc.Com/Pastoral/Church-Leaders-Pitfalls-1/>
- Prime, D. (1995). *Pastors and teachers*. Glasgow GB: Harper Collins.
- Still, W. (1996). *The work of the pastor*. Edinburgh, GB: Paternoster.
- Thompson, M. J. (1995). *Soul feast: An invitation to the Christian spiritual life*. Louisville, KY John Knox Press
- Whitney, D. (1991). *Spiritual discipline for the Christian life*. Colorado Springs: Navpress.
- Williams, D. (1997). *New concise bible dictionary*. Leicester, England: IVP.
- Youngblood, R. F. (1995). *New illustrated bible dictionary*. Oxford: Thomas Nelson Publishers